

Kosovo

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Kosovo, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Erasmus+ Country Fiche on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2017-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Erasmus+ Country fiche¹, the Kosovar higher education system comprises 5 types of HEIs:

- University is an institution of higher education which offers educational, scientific, research/artistic and professional programmes in at least five different subject areas and which has produced at least one graduate with an accredited doctorate in each of these programmes.
- University College is an institution of higher education which offers Bachelor, Master and Doctoral studies in at least three study areas. University Colleges offer professional and academic oriented programmes.
- College is an institution of higher education which offers professional or academic programmes at Bachelor and Master level.
- Higher professional schools offer professional courses in one or more professional fields at the Bachelor level, including programmes at level 5 according to NQF.
- Academies provide higher education and creative activity in specific areas of arts, sports or other professional areas at Bachelor and Master levels, including programmes at level 5 according to NQF.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. In total, about 38% of all Kosovar HEIs are Universities (*Universitet*), and only one of them, the University of Prishtina, has the right to award PhDs. Colleges (*Kolegje*) account for 57% of all Kosovar HEIs, however, none of them awards PhDs. Additionally, there is one Academy (*Akademia*), which does not award PhDs.

¹<https://erasmuspluskosovo.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Kosovo-Country-Fiche-2020.pdf>

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Academy	Akademia	1	1	0	0
College	Kolegje	12	0	12	0
University	Universitet	8	8	0	1
Total		21	9	12	1

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Kosovo's higher education and its evolution over time.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Figure 1 above shows that the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is recent and displays two distinct patterns of expansion. First, the oldest Kosovar university, the University of Prishtina, dates back

to 1969, and initiated the foundation of 8 Universities (*Universitet*) until 2010. The second wave of expansion can be observed between 2001 and 2012, when an extensive increase in Colleges (*Kolegje*) took place. The only Kosovar Academy was founded in 1999.

Students

In contrast to the number of institutions, in terms of the number of students enrolled, Universities (*Universitet*) account for almost 50% of all students and Colleges (*Kolegje*) for the other 50%.

According to different institutional mandates, we also observe systematic differences between educational levels: Colleges account for 53% of the bachelor students and 40% of the master students, while doctorates are within the remit of Universities.

The Academy plays a minor role being attended by 24 students. It only grants bachelor's degrees.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show first an increase with the number of enrolled students rising by 5% from 2017 to 2018. However, in 2019 three Universities (University of Prizren "Ukshin Hoti", University of Peja "Haxhi Zeka" and University of Mitrovica "Isa Boletini") did not meet the requirements for accreditation and the number of students decreased. Furthermore, only nine Colleges reported the number of students enrolled due to the Covid pandemic (including with the ABB College the largest College). In total the number of students reported declined therefore from 2018 to 2019 by 47%. In

2020 all Universities but also the ABB College reported again student numbers (while data for some smaller Colleges is still missing), bringing the total number of students back to about 90% of the level of 2018.

Figure 3. Share of students enrolled by institutional type

Note: University of Mitrovica "Isa Boletini", University of Peja "Haxhi Zeka" and University of Prizren "Ukshin Hoti" are missing in 2019

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